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COMPARISON OF TWO DIFFERENT ALPHA2 AGONISTS AS ADJUVANT IN BALANCED GENERAL ANAESTHESIA FOR HAEMODYNAMIC STABILITY & OLEGAMIC FIELD IN TRANSSPHENOIDAL PITUITARY ADENOMA REMOVAL IN TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: α_2 agonists are first approved by FDA for only sedation in ICU. But at present they are explored in various surgeries and in various routes.

In present study we evaluate efficacy of Clonidine and Dexmedetomidine in neuro anaesthesia for transsphenoidal removal of pituitary adenomas.

AIMS & OBJECTIVES: To evaluate efficacy of Clonidine and Dexmedetomidine in neuro anaesthesia for premedication, induction, haemodynamic stability, post-operative smooth extubation, recovery profile.

STUDY DESIGN: Randomised double blind observation study.

MATERIAL & METHODS: present study was done in V.S. general hospital & SVP hospital, N.H.L. municipal medical college, Ahmedabad in neurosurgery & Anaesthesia during 2015-2019. Adult 80 patients for elective surgery for pituitary adenoma transsphenoidal Removal patients grade 1 or 2 enrolled in study and they are randomly allocated to 2 groups. Randomisation done by odd & even number in seal opaque envelope. execution of randomisation at time of giving general anaesthesia.

In group C: patients had received Inj. Clonidine pre operatively 1 mcg/kg loading dose over 10 min by infusion pump followed by 0.5 mcg/kg/hr after intubation.

In group D: patients had received Inj. Dexmedetomidine pre operatively 1 mcg/kg loading dose over 10 min by infusion pump followed by maintenance infusion 0.5 mcg/kg/hr after intubation.

Patients are induced with Propofol 2 mg/kg and Inj. Atracurium 0.5 mg/kg and intubated with appropriate size endotracheal tube and maintained with O₂, N₂O, sevoflurane (0.2-0.5 MAC) in close circuit and Inj. Vecuronium bromide on Drager Fabius GS Work Station. In both the group infusion of drug was continued till dura closure by infusion pump.

OBSERVATION & RESULTS: In both the groups patients had stable haemodynamics and smooth post-operative recovery and extubation. Rate of reintubation was very less in both the groups.

CONCLUSION: α_2 agonists are good adjuvants for Transsphenoidal pituitary adenoma removal. Dexmedetomidine is better than Clonidine in Transsphenoidal pituitary adenoma removal.

KEYWORDS: Dexmedetomidine; Clonidine; Transsphenoidal approach of pituitary adenoma; Olegamic field; Haemodynamic Stability.

INTRODUCTION:

Tumours of pituitary gland represent approximately 10% of brain tumours & transsphenoidal approach of resection of same is done 20% of intracranial tumours worldwide.

Strategies for anaesthesia for transsphenoidal removal of pituitary adenomas is to provide Olegamic field, better haemodynamics, early extubation, smooth recovery, fast-tracking, short hospital stay. Patients of pituitary tumours have signs and symptoms of raised ICP, hypertension and increased stress response with altered glass glow coma scale. Fast tracking in neuro anaesthesia is challenging as we have to decrease ICP with better haemodynamics, proper depth of anaesthesia as well as early recovery and extubation. (7,8,9)

α -2 agonist like Dexmedetomidine and Clonidine were approved by FDA in 1999 for sedation in ICU. But they are now used in various anaesthesia techniques as an adjuvant. There are various studies suggesting advantageous role of Dexmedetomidine or Clonidine in neuro anaesthesia separately. Our aim of study was to compare both drugs as adjuvant in balanced anaesthesia for Transsphenoidal pituitary adenoma removal.

MATERIAL & METHODS:

After approval of institutional ethical committee and taking informed written consent of patient and relatives 80 patients of age group 18-50 yrs. posted for elective or emergency neurosurgeries of ASA grade 1 and 2 were enrolled in study and randomly allocated in 2 groups, group C and group D. Randomisation done simply by odd & even number.

All patients are preoperatively thoroughly assessed and investigated by routine investigation and specific investigations (CT scan, MRI). ABGA with electrolytes was done on the operative morning. In operation theatre, all monitors like electrocardiogram, noninvasive blood pressure, SPO₂, neuromuscular monitoring applied. 2 large bore venous cannulas were inserted.

Patients were premedicated with Inj. Glycopyrrolate 0.02 mcg/kg, Inj. Ondansetron 4 mg and Inj. Fentanyl 1 mcg/kg and Inj. Dexamethasone 8 mg.

Group allocation:

Group allocation was done simply by odd & even numbering of patients at the time of giving General Anaesthesia.

In group C, patients received Inj. Clonidine pre operatively 1 mcg/kg loading dose over 10 min by infusion pump followed by 0.5 mcg/kg/hr after intubation.

Group D, patients received Inj. Dexmedetomidine pre operatively 1 mcg/kg loading dose over 10 min by infusion pump followed by maintenance infusion 0.5 mcg/kg/hr after intubation.

Sample size calculation:

Change of ability of 40% to have Olegamic field by Boezaart scale was considered clinical significance.

We have done pilot study of 5 patients in each group. In dexmedetomidine group 1.1 \pm 0.2 scale out of 5 of Boezaart scale, & in Clonidine group 2.0 \pm 0.3 out of 5 of Boezaart scale. To detect mean difference of 1 out of 5, having 40% incidence difference to get Olegamic field, sample size of 40 in each group, Total 80 patients were enrolled.

Baseline and after premedication haemodynamic values are noted.

Patients were induced with Inj. Propofol 2 mg/kg and Inj. Atracurium 0.5 mg/kg and intubated with appropriate size endotracheal tube and maintained with O₂, N₂O, sevoflurane (1.2- 1.5 MAC) and Inj. Atracurium on Drager Fabius GS Work Station. Incremental dose of Inj. Atracurium was given according to neuromuscular monitoring. After intubation EtCO₂ was attached, as neurosurgeries were done in different position. Perioperative Awareness was monitored indirectly with increase in heart rate, blood pressure, sweating. Sevoflurane concentration was titrated accordingly to prevent awareness. Continuous monitoring of ECG, HR, SPO₂, EtCO₂ were done. NIBP and NM monitoring was done intermittently till end of surgery.

Intraoperative surgical field evaluation done by Boezaart scale (11) as follows:

0	No bleeding, virtually bloodless field
1	Slight bleeding, no suction required
2	Mild bleeding, occasionally suction required without interfering surgical field
3	Moderate bleeding, suctioning usually used, bleeding threatens surgical field but improves after suction
4	Heavy bleeding, suctioning frequently used, bleeding threatens surgical field directly after suction is removed.
5	Severe bleeding, bleeding appears faster than suction & is uncontrollable.

Bradycardia and hypotension were defined as 30% decreased in baseline values.

Bradycardia was treated with inj. Atropine 0.6 mg iv stat. And hypotension was treated by decrease in the dose of infusion of α_2 agonist. Incremental dose of Inj. Atracurium was given according to NMJ monitoring.

Total requirement of sevoflurane was calculated during surgery.

Infusion of drug was stopped at the closure of dura. Reversal was given after regaining of spontaneous respiration and guided with NMJ monitoring. Patients were extubated after regaining of adequate muscle tone and power, spontaneous tidal volume, reflexes. Time duration between reversal and extubation was noted. Patients were watched for Alderte criteria and Fast-tracking criteria for recovery. Patients were shifted to post-operative postoperative ward and monitored for 24 hours. Postoperative analgesia was given in the form of Inj. paracetamol 10 mg/kg. and postoperative analgesic requests in 24 hours were noted

Table: 1. Fast track criteria¹⁰

Level of consciousness	
-awake and oriented	2
-arousable with minimum stimulation	1
-responsive only for tactile stimulation	0
Physical activity	
-able to move all extremities on command	2
-some weakness in movement of extremities	1
-unable to voluntarily move extremities	0
Haemodynamic stability	
-Blood pressure <15% of baseline MAP value	2
-Blood pressure 15%-30% of baseline MAP value	1
-Blood pressure >30% of baseline MAP value	0
Respiratory stability	
-Able to breathe deeply	2
-Tachypnea with good cough	1
-Dyspneic with weak cough	0
Oxygen saturation	
-Maintain value >90% on room air	2
-Requires supplemental oxygen to maintain oxygen saturation >90%	1

-Saturation <90% with supplemental oxygen	0
Post-operative pain assessment	
-None or mild discomfort	2
-Moderate to severe pain controlled with IV analgesics	1
-persistent severe pain	0
Post-operative emetic symptoms	
-None/mild nausea with no active vomiting	2
-Transient vomiting controlled with IV antiemetics	1
-Persistent moderate to severe nausea and vomiting	0
Total score	14

Table: 2. Aldrete criteria (10)

Respiratory stability	
-Able to take deep breath and cough	2
-Dyspnea/shallow breathing	1
-Apnea	0
Oxygen saturation	
-Maintain value >92% on room air	2
-Needs o2 inhalation to maintain Spo2 >90%	1
-Spo2 <90% even with supplemental oxygen	0
Contiguousness	
-Fully awake	2
-arousable on calling	1

Not responding	0
Circulation	
-BP±20 mm Hg preop	2
-BP±20-50 mm Hg preop	1
-BP±50 mm Hg preop	0
Activity	
-Able to move 4 extremities	2
-Able to move 2 extremities	1
-Able to move 0 extremities	0
Total score	10

Surgeon satisfaction score was noticed as:

1. Bad .2 Moderate 3. Good 4. Excellent

OBSERVATIONS & RESULTS:

Patient parameters including age, weight, ASA status, gender, duration of surgery and anaesthesia, blood loss, Boezaart bleeding scale & end tidal sevoflurane% are shown in the table-3.

Table 3: Baseline Parameters of patients

Parameters	Group D (n=40)	Group C (n=40)	P value
Age (Years)	41.2±10.8	42.7±11.8	>0.05
Gender (M: F)	24/16	23/17	>0.05
Weight (Kg)	72.2±11.	69.7±12.5	>0.05
ASA status (1/2)	636 /4	31/9	>0.05
Duration of surgery (Duration min) of	120.1±4	126.8±52.	>0.05
anaesthesia (min)Total blood loss (ml)	9.9165.2±3	9169.2±32.	>0.05
Boezaart bleeding scaleEnd -tidal sevoflurane (%)	8.71.32±0.4	81.38±0.45	>0.05
Surgeon satisfaction score	31.21±0.3	1.22±0.32	>0.05
	3.2±0.5	2.9±0.9	>0.05

Table 4. Heart Rate in both groups

Heart Rate	Group D	Group C	P value
Baseline	90.6±2.8	92.34±3.51	>0.05
At Induction	88.25±1.28	91.26±4.24	>0.05
15 min	75.21±1.16	86.26±3.21	>0.05
30 min	71.35±2.18	76.52±2.32	>0.05
60 min	69.21±2.11	74.12±3.22	>0.05
120 min	67.23±1.63	71.44±2.31	>0.05
At extubation	66.16±1.73	70.24±1.58	>0.05
At PACU	70.15±2.24	70.21±1.56	>0.05

Table 5. Mean Arterial Pressure in both groups

Mean Arterial Pressure	Group D	Group C	P value
Baseline	112.68±2.58	116.12±5.8	>0.05
At Induction	108.22±2.58	110.26±2.9	>0.05
15 min	79.28±5.56	84.28±2.9	>0.05
30 min	76.22±5.11	80.21±1.8	>0.05
60 min	74.28±5.10	76.55±4.5	>0.05
120 min	78.40±4.10	77.51±2.8	>0.05
At extubation	80.26±3.30	81.28±2.4	>0.05
At PACU	96.28±2.4	98.22±1.8	>0.05

Table 6: Fast-track & Alderte criteria at Extubation

		Group D	Group C	P value
Extubation time	Min	(n=40)7.6±1.14	(n=40)12.6±1.51	<0.001
Post extubation 5 min	FTC	10.8±1.6	10.2±1.8	>0.05
	AC	7.1±1.7	6.5±1.5	>0.05

Post extubation 10 min	FTC	12.2±1.6	12.5±1.5	>0.05
	AC	8.7±1.1	8.4±1.5	>0.05
Post extubation 15 min	FTC	12.5±1.8	12.7±0.9	>0.05
	AC	9.7±0.2	8.9±1.1	>0.05
Post extubation 30 min	FTC	12.8±0.8	12.8±0.5	>0.05
	AC	9.8±0.1	9.1±0.6	>0.05

In primary outcome variables mean extubation time was shorter in group D than that of group C. otherwise FTC and AC were comparable in both the groups post extubation 5,10,15 and 30 mins. ABGA was done post operatively 30 min after extubation and compared with baseline ABGA. All patients were monitored in PACU for 24 hours. Oxygenation by vent mask was done.

Postoperative parameters:

Postoperative analgesic requests within 24 hours were more in group C (3.4±0.5) compared to group D (2.4±0.5). no patient had neurosurgical complication requiring early reoperation. No patient had any complication like shivering, vomiting, respiratory depression or have any episodes of hypoxia.

DISCUSSION

Present study compared the effect of two different α_2 agonists dexmedetomidine and clonidine in neurosurgical patients of pituitary adenomas in attempt to find clinically feasible combination of anaesthetics that would provide perioperative haemodynamic stability and fast recovery without respiratory depression. Addition of α_2 agonists reduce requirement of volatile anaesthetic agent. Fast tracking in surgery and anaesthesia for intracranial tumours balances the ICP, BP, CBF changes and early and satisfactory outcome in form of neurophysiological and neurocognitive function as well as it decreases the hospital stay of the patient.

Aim of the study was to compare efficacy of two α_2 agonists dexmedetomidine and clonidine in anaesthesia for trans nasal pituitary adenoma removal added in form of premedication and pre-operative infusion for stable haemodynamics, smooth recovery and fast tracking.

The antinociceptive, sympatholytic and anaesthesia sparing effects of α_2 agonists are well documented.(1) This spectrum of properties would be consistent with the important goals during neurosurgical anaesthesia of intraoperative haemodynamic stability and modulation of intraoperative sympathetic response to attenuate cerebrovascular and myocardial risks and avoid antra cranial haemorrhage(2'3), and to allow immediate neurological evaluation upon emergence(4). Physiologically α_2 receptors are located presynaptic, post synaptic and extra synoptical. Pre synoptical receptors are responsible for more clinical impact as they regulate nor adrenaline and ATP release through negative feedback mechanism. α_2 receptor are also present in periphery as in pletlets, liver, kidney, eye, etc. pharmacologically studies show that Dexmedetomidine is 8 times more specific α_2 adenoreceptor than

Clonidine. α_2 : α_1 activity 1620:1 for Dexmedetomidine and 220:1 for clonidine. Dexmedetomidine acts supraspinally on locus ceruleus α_2 receptors directly in spinal cord, so inhibit the nociception. Substantia geletenosa of spinal cord of dorsal horn contains α_2 receptors. When stimulated inhibit firing of nociceptive neurons stimulated by A \bar{i} and c fibers and also inhibits substance-P¹, so it provides better haemodynamic control and intense analgesia. Clonidine also prevents increase in ICP by controlling haemodynamic changes.

Udelsman et al (12) showed responses to HPA axis during controlled Surgical & Anaesthesia stress.

Gonul Keles & Ment ozer used dexmedetomidine infusion for fast tracking for spine surgery (9) & other surgeries. (13) Our experience with both the drugs to control haemodynamics was good.

Gopalakrishna KN (14), used Dexmedetomidine for transnasal pituitary adenoma removal & concluded that it provides olegamic field& haemodynamic stability.

Salimi A, et al (15) have used Dexmedetomidine for transnasal pituitary adenoma removal for olegamic field, & also suggested that it provides surgeon satisfaction more. But in Clonidine group extubation was late ($P<0.001$). it was $7.6+1.14$ min in group D and $12.6+1.51$ in group C. otherwise fast tracking and alderite criteria were fulfilled same in both groups ($P>0.05$).

Limitations of our study were there was no control group& non availability of SSEP, ICP monitoring. No patient in both groups need reintubation. Overall outcome was good & fast tracked in both groups in terms of surgical & anaesthesia outcome.

CONCLUSION:

In nutshell both dexmedetomidine & clonidine are good adjuvants fast-track anaesthesia for pituitary tumours removal through transsphenoidal route; in terms of better haemodynamic stability; providing Olegamic field, smooth emergence; better past operative recovery.

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